

	Deliverable Title PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS	Ref. D5.2	Issue A
	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary COMPOSITADOUR	Work Package WP5	Date 18/12/2020

Object: Project deliverable

PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 886549. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

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MODIFICATIONS INDEX

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1. Introduction

1.1. Generic introduction

The FRAMES (Fibre Reinforced thermoplastic Manufacturing for stiffened, complex, double curved Structures) project, supported by Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking and the DLR, intend to develop advanced knowledge and manufacturing solutions for a full scale thermoplastic aircraft rear end.

The project is part of the Clean Sky 2 initiative focused on developing concepts and enabling technologies for an optimum rear fuselage and empennage. FRAMES main objective is to validate and assess a manufacturing approach of an integral thermoplastic rear end with critical design features. Key technologies developed within FRAMES will be used into a mid-scale advanced rear end demonstrator manufactured by the Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR), part of a Clean Sky 2 technology platform for large passenger aircrafts.

FRAMES consortium relies on a strong partnership of leading European Industries and research organization in the area of aerospace and composites materials processing.

Project was launched on July 2020 and targets to deliver a xenon heating device simulation model for thermoplastic composites fiber placement, efficient double curved TP-stiffeners manufacturing solution and associated prototypes as well as a self-heating tooling equipment able to perform a co-consolidation of the skin and stiffeners in one shot.

1.2. Contacts

1.2.1. COMPOSITADOUR

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1.3. Abbreviations

EU : European Union

FRAMES : Fibre Reinforced thermoplastic Manufacturing for stiffened, complex, double curved Structures

PDER : Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results

PGA : Project General Assembly

JU : Joint Undertaking

1.4. Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results/ communication activity related to the project must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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2. Scope of the document

This document corresponds to the first version of the deliverable Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER) and has been prepared following Horizon 2020 guidelines. The PDER summarises FRAMES Consortium’s strategy and concrete actions related to the protection, dissemination and exploitation of the project results. The PDER is a living document and follows the evolution of the project from the project start until the submission of the final project report. The PDER will need to be updated during the implementation of the project and, FRAMES consortium will periodically report to the European Commission and the Topic Manager the concrete dissemination and exploitation activities carried out. These activities need to be consistent with the PEDR and proportionate to the impact expected from the action. At the end of the project the final report should include the final version of the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results that will allow the European Commission to assess the impact of the project.

As highlighted by the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, “it is essential that the public investment in these activities is converted into socio-economic benefits for the society. This idea is reflected in the Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation with a clear accent to the beneficiaries’ obligations to exploit and disseminate the outcomes of the funded activities.”¹

Focusing on terminology and for efficient outcomes of these activities, it is needed to remind the main difference between Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation:

- Communication : Measures to promote the action itself and its results to multiple audiences, to inform and reach out the society showing the benefits of research. It is about European added value of the project. It reaches a wide audience including media and general public, therefore, it is important to adapt the language to non-specialist audience
- Dissemination : It is the public disclosure of project results by any appropriate means to audience that may use and uptake the results in their own work (scientific community, industry, stakeholders, professional organizations, policy makers)
- Exploitation : it is the utilisation of results by stakeholders into further research activities other than those covered by the action, or into the development, the creation and the marketing of a product, a process or a service. It could be as well serve to standardisation activities.

Those three activities are relevant all along the project duration but will become more consistent by the second half of the project timeframe, with delivery of concrete project results. The FRAMES Consortium are committed to exploit project results beyond the project completion up to four year as mentioned in the Grant Agreement. Therefore, the PDER details a strategy with concrete actions to maximize project impacts.

3. Internal communication

Internal communication is based on regular meetings between Frames consortium members themselves but also with the topic manager. A data repository is used to facilitate internal communication activities.

Monthly, the project coordinator organizes the project general assembly composed of representatives of the consortium partners, to assess project progress and take all decisions concerning project

¹ <http://www.iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/Fact-Sheet-Plan-for-the-Exploitation-and-Dissemination-of-Results-H2020.pdf>

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strategy, budget, dissemination and exploitation strategy in their legitimate interests and their commitments.

Every 6-month the project coordinator organize a face to face meeting between the topic manager and FRAMES consortium.

Additional meetings between partners and between the consortium and the topic manager may occurs over the project duration, whether in face to face or in remote by Teams, Webex or Skype for example.

A project dedicated SharePoint repository is used to share documents and facilitate data collection and exchanges among partners.

4. External communication and dissemination

Basic rules for communication and dissemination activities are detailed within the Grant Agreement. It is mandatory for all beneficiaries to disseminate its results (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results) by appropriate means unless it goes against their legitimate interests.

“This does not change the obligation detailed into the Grant Agreement, in particular the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.”²

Dissemination of results has to be carefully balanced between strategic proprietary know-how strengthening partner position and the opportunity to reach a wide audience stimulating research initiatives and emerging applications.

Basic rules for dissemination states:

- “A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.”
- “Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.”

The approach for an efficient dissemination and exploitation of FRAMES results is presented in the following sections.

4.1. Objectives

Communication and dissemination aims to reach attention to different stakeholders on the project concepts, progress and achievements. Industrial partners involved into aeronautics, transportation in general but also from the composites industry are already identified, but research and scientific community are key targets too.

The main points of the FRAMES dissemination strategy are to:

- Demonstrate that FRAMES key outcomes are bringing validated industrial solutions to meet future aircrafts production challenges

² FRAMES Grant Agreement 886549

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- Highlight the engineering and industrial capabilities of each FRAMES partners
- Reassert the commitment of EU to support projects tackling societal challenges

4.2. Key messages

The key messages to define will serve the three activities Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, and are intended to identify as clear as possible the FRAMES initiative. Key messages initially identified are:

- Optical-thermal simulation tool for fiber placement
- High rate composite manufacturing solutions
- Thermoplastic double curved skin-stiffeners structure
- Skin-stiffeners co-consolidation in one shot
- Self-heated tooling solution

Key messages may be updated during project timeframe, to precise or highlights others aspects.

4.3. Target audience

Identified FRAMES stakeholders are classified into four main categories:

[A] : **Manufacturing professional stakeholders throughout the supply chain** : to create business opportunities, potential collaboration but also provide useful feedback on project development

Aircrafts manufacturers and major aircrafts OEMs

Thermoplastic composites suppliers

Relevant SMEs

[B] : **R&D Community** : to contribute to enhance project visibility, stimulate research initiatives and provide feedback on project development

Other thermoplastic composites R&D initiatives and demonstrators

Scientific and Academic audience

European technology platforms

European commission

[C] : **International standards developers & influential associations** : to support aeronautics and composites applications, give project achievements feedback and help to build up funding strategies for next steps

Standardization bodies

International organizations

[D] : **General audience / society** : to reach interest into technical and industrial activities, highlight European collaborations, and support new technologies acceptance

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4.4. Detailed plan

A first release of the detailed plan for communication and dissemination activities is presented in Tableau 1.

4.5. Implementation

4.5.1. Visibility of JU funding

Unless the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results/communication activity related to the project (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must display the JU logo, display the EU emblem, include the following acknowledgment and the following the disclaimer :

Acknowledgement (for dissemination and communication)

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 886549. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

Acknowledgement (for infrastructure, equipment and major results)

This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 886549. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results/communication activity related to the project must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.5.2. Digital communications and social medias

FRAMES activities will be released using both regional and global medias, dedicated to professionals and general public, to reach maximum audience.

Partners websites : Each project member will use their own website to communicate and disseminate on the project.

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Heraeus Noblelight Ltd. joins the FRAMES project: Reducing aircraft emissions with lightweight thermoplastic composites

Heraeus Noblelight joins the FRAMES project, part of the Clean Sky 2 program, the largest European research programme developing innovative, cutting-edge technology aimed at reducing CO2, gas emissions and noise levels produced by aircrafts. The project therefore researches the usage of thermoplastic composites for a lightweight aircraft rear fuselage and empennage. The FRAMES applied research project is scheduled for 2.5 years. FRAMES stands for Fiber reinforced thermoplastics manufacturing for stiffened, complex, doubled curved structure.

Torsten Jenek Head of Innovation Optics and Flash at Heraeus Noblelight commented: "Heraeus acknowledges its environmental responsibility. Carbon composites contribute to more sustainable air travel and the reduction of CO2 footprint. Heraeus' humm3"

Figure 1 : FRAMES communication on Heraeus company website ([link](#))

Technopole Pays Basque : Dedicated to promote and communicate on activities carried out by local companies around Estia-Compositadour facilities.

<https://www.technopolepaysbasque.fr/fr/4-sites-technopolitains/technocite/actualite/compositadour-coordonne-un-projet-europeen-de-rd-dans-laeronautique.html>

JEC Group : The world leading media and events company entirely dedicated to promote the development of the composites material industry, through knowledge, networking and innovation.

<http://www.jecomposites.com/knowledge/international-composites-news/european-consortium-develop-aerospace-thermoplastic>

European consortium to develop aerospace thermoplastic manufacturing solutions for complex geometries

22 SEP 2020

A consortium of European companies initiated by ESTIA-Compositadour is joining forces to develop advanced knowledge and manufacturing solutions for a full-scale thermoplastic aircraft rear end demonstrator.

Full thermoplastic Advanced Rear End demonstrator

The fuselage of the next generation of large passenger aircrafts will certainly rely on the benefits of thermoplastic composites. Greater toughness, recycling potential and faster production cycles enable the capacity to meet future aviation sector challenges.

Figure 2 : FRAMES communication on JEC website

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Composites World : The media brand for fiber-reinforced composites technology, focused on connecting market leaders to reliable, accessible information about processes and trends across the global composites manufacturing industry.

<https://www.compositesworld.com/news/frames-full-scale-thermoplastic-composite-aircraft-rear-end-demonstrator>

9/24/2020 | 1 MINUTE READ

FRAMES: Full-scale thermoplastic composite aircraft rear-end demonstrator

Clean Sky 2 project led by ESTIA-Compositadour will develop enabling technologies for optimum rear fuselage and empennage.

#cleansky #nextgenairspace

GINGER GARDINER
Senior Editor, CompositesWorld

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- > 2020 CW Top Shops recognizes top-performing facilities
- > Part 2: Applying CT scan data analysis and visualization to composites
- > Cloudy skies ahead for composites

Thermoplastic composite Advanced Rear End (ARE) demonstrator for Clean Sky 2. Photo Credit: ESTIA-Compositadour

CW COLLECTIONS

Download CW's Thermoplastic Composites Collection

FRAMES: A new research project focused on thermoplastic manufacturing solutions for complex geometries. A consortium of European companies initiated by ESTIA-Compositadour (Bayonne, France) is joining forces to develop advanced knowledge and manufacturing solutions for a full-scale thermoplastic aircraft rear end demonstrator.

The fuselage of the next generation of large passenger aircraft could exploit the benefits of thermoplastic composites (TPCs) — including increased toughness, recyclability and faster production cycles — to meet future aviation sector challenges.

Figure 3 : FRAMES communication on CompositesWorld media

CORDIS : The European Research and Development service for funded projects results source, with aims to promote open science, create innovative services and products and stimulate European growth.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/886549>

LinkedIn : Global professional social media, promoting networking and business opportunities around the world.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/compositadour_frames-fuselage-activity-6713807465860878336-Rf5E/

Twitter : World known microblogging, news and social networking service

<https://twitter.com/EstiaOfficiel/status/1308306839839207424>

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Facebook : World known news and social networking service
<https://fr-fr.facebook.com/ingenieurs.estia/>

4.5.3. Events

FRAMES partners plan to attend the following events to raise interests about project objectives and activities, technologies involved, results achieved and provide specific highlights on partners capacities and collaboration.

ITHEC : International Conference & Exhibition on thermoplastic composites, Bremen (DE)

<https://ithec.de/>

Specifically focused in the field of thermoplastic composites and structural lightweight construction.

2020 edition : 387 participants, 55 exhibitors, 100 lectures

Composites Meetings : Business convention for composite manufacturers and users, Nantes (FR)

<https://france.compositesmeetings.com/index.php/fr/>

BtoB event for composites materials suppliers and end users.

JEC World : International trade show dedicated to composite materials and applications, Paris (FR)

<https://www.jec-world.events/>

Showcases, business meetings, networking and conferences

Previous edition: 1300 exhibitors, 112 countries, 43500 professionals visits

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SIAE Paris Air Show : International Paris Air Show, Paris (FR), is a trade and air show organized by French aerospace industry's primary representative body, and the largest air show and aerospace industry exhibition event in the world.

<https://www.siae.fr/en/presentation.htm>

2019 edition : 2453 exhibitors from 49 countries, 316470 visitors (139840 trade visitors from 185 countries and 176630 general public)

Forum Aerospace Valley : Annual meeting of Aerospace Valley cluster members, with conferences, round tables, business meetings and networking for SME, startups and companies leaders, 2021 edition to be held in Biarritz (FR)

<https://forum.aerospace-valley.com/>

Previous edition : 500 participants, 600 BtoB meetings, 24 exhibitors

ICCM : International Conference on Composites Materials, 2021 edition to be held in Belfast (UK)

<https://iccm23.org/>

Dedicated to leading researchers and scientists and focused on reporting latest developments in the advancements and exploitation of wide range of composites materials and structures.

2019 edition : 1513 presentations, coming from 50 countries

ECCM : European Conference on Composite Materials, 2022 edition to be held in Lausanne (CH).

Forum for accessing up-to-date knowledge from both industrial and academics activities in all the fields of composites materials. Plenary talks, keynotes lectures, posters presentations.

Previous edition : 1200 participants

ACM : International Symposium on Automated Composites Manufacturing, 2021 edition to be held in Bristol (UK)

<https://www.acm5.org/>

Conferences with academics and industry partners around advanced automated composites manufacturing processes.

ISCM : International Symposium on Composites Manufacturing for high performance applications, 9th edition to be held in Stade (DE)

<https://iscm2021.besl-eventservice.de/>

Presentations and discussions to promote recent developments in manufacturing of high performance composites and related areas.

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4.5.4. Publications and press release

A part of FRAMES research activities and public-released results will be also published in the scientific journal Composites Part A, as well as released in open access to the Zenodo repository.

Composites Part A : Scientific journal for applied science and manufacturing dealing will all science and technology aspects of composites materials, with publications of research papers, review articles, case studies, short communications and letters.

Zenodo : Open access repository for European Community funded research, managing a wide range of file types, contents including metadata management.

5. Exploitation strategy

5.1. Exploitation plan strategy and target audience

Main objectives for the exploitation of FRAMES project results are to :

- Develop and propose commercial solutions issued from Key Exploitable Results (KER) with identified markets targets
- Use KER and knowledge gained into new research and development activities, funded or not.
- Use KER and knowledge gained into new or updated educational and training courses

5.2. Identification of project results and IP management

FRAMES consortium intends to turn their participation and the project outcomes into profit (building a common strategy based on the FRAMES outputs), and to launch new activities, thanks to the knowledge gained. Exploitation will ensure that partners will work towards a successful technology and knowledge transfer for market uptake. It will ensure high visibility and promotion of the project and its results during its execution and after its end.

Although additional development work will be needed before the project results are subject to a commercial exploitation, a preliminary analysis of the exploitation strategy and IPR has been already done. FRAMES Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that will be mainly benefiting for the aeronautic sector, and in particular, to manufacturers of rear end parts have been identified and are presented below. The IPR and exploitation claims associated with respective KERs are also indicated:

- Intellectual Property Rights: Background (B); Foreground (F).
- Exploitation Claims: the intention of the partner to exploit the results by: Making them and selling them (M); Using them internally to make something else for sale (U); License them to 3rd parties (L); provide services such as consultancy or knowledge transfer (O)

Exploitable results	Type	Partners involved	Benefit for users	Exploitation strategy
R1. Optical and thermal simulation model for power/speed sequence generation	Software	Heraeus/ ESTIA	Availability of new simulation tool for fiber placement with xenon flashlamp heating device	Integrating into industry partners processes to improve manufacturing accuracy and products (BF/MO)
R2. TP Stiffeners manufacturing processes	Process	All	Optimized and robust manufacturing process for complex thermoplastic stiffeners	Methods and approach to be integrated into current existing manufacturing processes. Consultancy (BF/ULO). Identification of results worth patenting in EU and US to strengthen the status of partners as developers and key technology and products suppliers.
R3. CF-PEKK stringers, beam, clips and Z-Frames	Product	All	Solutions for aerospace quality thermoplastic stiffeners with increased complexity New options for increased integration level of composites structures, and part number reduction	Parts to be incorporated into next generation commercial aircrafts (BF/MUO) Use parts demonstrators in fairs to provide added value versus market competitors
R4. Self heated tooling solution for highly integrated thermoplastic stiffened panels	Technology/process	All	Novel self heated tooling solution allowing both steps : fast skin lay up, and co-consolidation of skin and stiffeners in one shot step using benefits from thermoplastics Faster manufacturing processes compare to post assembly steps, and enhanced skin-stiffeners interface	Tooling solution provided for industrial applications to manufacturer of thermoplastic stiffened panels (BF/MULO) Consultancy Identification of results worth patenting in EU and US to strengthen the status of partners as developers and key tooling technology suppliers.

Table 1 : Key Exploitable Results and associated benefits and exploitation strategy

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5.3. Exploitation plan

As FRAMES is still at an early stage of project activities, no mature results have yet reached a mature state suitable for exploitation. Therefore, exploitation assessment is limited to the definition of expected results and first approach of future exploitation of project outputs, presented by FRAMES partners :

Partner	Foreground-Exploitable outcome	Exploitation interest	Advantages
ESTIA	<p>Focus on TP advanced processes since the last 5 years</p> <p>Development of advanced skills and know-how in both TP parts manufacturing processes using xenon flash lamp heating and co-consolidation approach</p>	<p>Use knowledge in future research work/research projects</p> <p>Reinforce the range of technological services</p> <p>Provide knowledge transfer</p> <p>Create possibility of patenting and licensing technologies</p>	<p>Contribution to strengthen ESTIA position in fiber reinforced thermoplastics at national and European level</p> <p>Increase platform revenues through new contracts</p> <p>Diversification of potential applications, not limited to aeronautics like spatial or automotive</p>
HERAEUS	<p>Software optical thermal simulation model that allow to specify correct flash lamp parameters for AFP lay up</p> <p>Demonstration of xenon flash lamp system to be a reliable and high performance alternative to laser heating system for TP aerospace applications</p>	<p>Provide the knowledge and evidence required by the composites industry on the operation of the Xenon flashlamp heating technology</p> <p>Maintain HERAEUS' position as the leader and technical authority on xenon flash lamp heating systems</p> <p>Expand working relationships with project partners and topic manager</p> <p>Provide general evidence of the heating capabilities of the humm3® technology</p>	<p>Stronger technical team at HERAEUS</p> <p>Stronger relationships with partners</p> <p>Technical evidence of humm3® technology performance for prospective customers</p>
XELIS	<p>Demonstration of reliable concept that thermoplastic can overcome hurdles of requirements which are</p>	<p>Investing in infrastructure and skilled employees it is important to have support in investments of the product at the same time. XELIS is aware</p>	<p>Reduced financial risk of development, partnering with companies in the same field of development to</p>

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	<p>relevant for lightweight aviation design.</p> <p>Efficient production of long parts with reduced wall thickness like stringers</p> <p>Efficient production of short parts with increased curvature like frames</p> <p>Efficient production of parts with thickness variations like skins</p>	<p>of a variety of parts in future aircrafts being suitable for material transition taking advantage of improved material properties of high-quality thermoplastic polymers. Volumes are today in a niche, because the proof of industrialized production is missing.</p>	<p>join forces and reach a bigger audience.</p>
CERO	<p>CERO is already focusing on thermoplastic composites and aim to go a step further with tooling shapes complexity and moulding temperature ranges</p> <p>Demonstration to the aviation and thermoplastic industry that co consolidation tooling technology is now able to apply to complex panels with cross stiffening members and ready for expected production rates</p> <p>Evidence of integrated heating with complex shapes and autonomous tooling to support current Out Of Autoclave trend at a glance</p>	<p>Maintain CERO' position as a leader on thermoplastics and composites tooling solution</p> <p>Expand and enhance the working relationships with the project partners, the Topic Leader and suppliers</p> <p>Use knowledge gain for further R&D activities or collaborative projects</p>	<p>Better visibility on the European industrial and thermoplastic market.</p> <p>Support to internal R&D.</p> <p>Stronger relationships with the consortium members.</p>

Table 2 : FRAMES initial exploitation plan

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6. Conclusion

FRAMES plan for dissemination and exploitation of results provides an overview of the dissemination strategy and guidelines for proper exploitation of results generated during and after the project. It is intended to be updated with coming project results and achievements.

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7. Annexes

7.1. FRAMES detailed plan for dissemination and communication activities

Type of action	Details of action	Estimated date of completion	Location (if applicable)	Target audience	Expected impacts	Leader
Digital communication	Publication on project launch on ESTIA LinkedIn account	September 2020	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/compositadour_frames-fuselage-activity-6713807465860878336-Rf5E/	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New contacts with potential end customers New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities Raise interest of potential talents and students Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative 	ESTIA
Digital communication	Publications of project progress and on-going work on ESTIA LinkedIn account	Every 6 months	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/compositadour	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New contacts with potential end customers New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities Raise interest of potential talents and students Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative 	ESTIA
Digital communication	Article on project launch on local digital media : https://www.technopolepay-sbasque.fr	October 2020	https://www.technopolepay-sbasque.fr/fr/4-sites-technopolitains/technocite/actualite/compositadour-coordonne-un-projet-europeen-de-rd-dans-laeronautique.html	General society, local authorities, local industries and SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New contacts with potential industrial partners Strengthen relationships with local authorities, influence policy priorities and regional development strategies Raise interest of potential talents 	ESTIA

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Digital communication	Articles on project launch on Estia website	September 2020	https://www.estia.fr/les-actualites/frames-a-new-research-project-focused-on-thermoplastic-manufacturing-solutions-for-complex-geometries	Students, R&D community, local authorities	Further R&D activities through collaborative projects or master thesis Strengthen relationships with local authorities, influence policy priorities and regional development strategies Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA
Digital communication	Article on project launch on Estia Facebook account	September 2020	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/ingenieurs.estia/	Students, General society	Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA
Digital communication	Publications of project progress and on-going work on Estia Facebook account	Every 6 months	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/ingenieurs.estia/	Students, General society	Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA
Digital communication	Article on project launch on Estia Twitter account	September 2020	https://twitter.com/EstiaOfficiel/status/1308306839839207424	Students, General society	Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA
Digital communication	Publications of project progress and on-going work on Estia Twitter account	Every 6 months	https://twitter.com/estiaofficiel	Students, General society	Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA
Digital communication	Article on project launch on Heraeus website	September 2020	https://www.heraeus.com/en/hng/company_hng_1/press/2020_hng_press/frames_project_humm3.html	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, General society	New contacts with potential end customers New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Raise interest of potential talents and students	HERAEUS

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Digital communication	Fact sheet on CORDIS	April 2020	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/886549	R&D centers, European and local Public authorities	New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities	ESTIA
Dissemination material	Publication of press releases on JEC Magazine	September 2020 and every 6 month	http://www.jeccomposites.com/knowledge/international-composites-news/european-consortium-develop-aerospace-thermoplastic	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	New contacts with potential end customers New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities Raise interest of potential talents and students Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative	ESTIA
Dissemination material	Publication of press releases on Composites World	September 2020 and every 6 month	https://www.compositesworld.com/news/frames-full-scale-thermoplastic-composite-aircraft-rear-end-demonstrator	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	New contacts with potential end customers New contacts with potential industrial partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities Raise interest of potential talents and students Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative	ESTIA
Dissemination material	Publication of peer-reviewed article in scientific journal Composites Part A	September 2021	-	R&D centers, Scientific community	New contacts with potential R&D partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Raise interest of potential talents and students	HERAEUS
Dissemination material	Publication of scientific article in FRAMES Zenodo repository with open access	September 2021	-	R&D centers, Scientific community	New contacts with potential R&D partners Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects Raise interest of potential talents and students	ESTIA

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Dissemination material	Promotional video to be shared on social medias, specialized magazines and partners websites	September 2021	-	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA
Dissemination material	Poster or Kakemono to be show during events participations	December 2021	-	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European and local Public authorities, General society	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA
Dissemination material	Highlight on specific FRAMES technologies and manufacturing solutions into student training courses	September 2021	-	Students	Knowledge sharing	ESTIA
Event	Participation at ITHEC 2020	October 13-15, 2020	Virtual event	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	XELIS
Event	Participation at ITHEC 2022	October 2022	Bremen (DE)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p>	XELIS

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					<p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	
Event	Participation at Composites Meetings 2021	November 2021	Nantes (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	CERO
Event	Participation at JEC World 2021	June 1-3, 2021	Paris (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA
Event	Participation at JEC World 2022	March 2022	Paris (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA
Event	Participation at JEC World 2023	March 2023	Paris (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p>	ESTIA

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					<p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	
Event	Participation at SIAE Paris Air Show 2023	June 2023	Paris - Le Bourget (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, European Public authorities	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Influence policy priorities and aviation development strategies</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA
Event	Participation at Forum Aerospace Valley	May 2021	Biarritz (FR)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, Local Public authorities, local SMEs	<p>New contacts with potential industrial partners</p> <p>Strengthen relationships with local authorities, influence policy priorities and regional development strategies</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents</p>	ESTIA
Event	Participation at ICCM24	August 2022	Belfast (UK)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, Scientific community	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial or scientific partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	HERAEUS
Event	Participation at ECCM20	June 2022	Lausanne (CH)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, Scientific community	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial or scientific partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	HERAEUS

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Event	Participation at ACM5	April 2021	Bristol (UK)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, Scientific community	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial or scientific partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	HERAEUS
Event	Participation at ISCM21	April 2021	Stade (DE)	Aerospace OEMs and Tier1, Composites industry, R&D centers, Scientific community	<p>New contacts with potential end customers</p> <p>New contacts with potential industrial or scientific partners</p> <p>Further R&D activities within direct contracts or through collaborative projects</p> <p>Knowledge sharing</p> <p>Increased visibility of FRAMES partners capabilities</p> <p>Raise interest of potential talents and students</p> <p>Increased visibility of EU support and Clean Sky initiative</p>	ESTIA

Tableau 1 : Detailed plan for communication and dissemination activities

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